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Research on the self-trust of engineering students

INTRODUCTION

Education should be able to train students with skills and competences that meet the expectations of the labour market during the study period.

Both higher education and recently graduated students are facing serious challenges presented by the 21st century labour market. Many competences are defined by employers as required, out of which *creativity*, *innovation* and *entrepreneurship* are key competences in most professional areas. This is especially true for the engineering profession since accelerated technical and technological progress in the 21st century presents a task to be solved for engineering education.

The purpose of the correlation research is to present, based on a pilot survey, the students' self-assessment of their own skills and achievements as key factors of self-trust, and compare these measurement results with those of senior business leaders in the same sector. The survey focuses on the existence of self-trust, one of the basic conditions for the key competences expected by the labour market.

The research is based on the hypothesis that engineering students on their way to enter the labour market are unaware of their own abilities and their self-trust needs improving. The significance of the subject is provided by the fact that students with higher self-trust can be more successful and are more consciously able to plan their professional goals and career. It is important to have long term goals in order to knowingly plan studies, optional subjects and competences to be improved. To do this, students need to have realistic self-assessment and self-image and as a result they must have a healthy self-trust.

In the framework of the current research which is the primary examination of an international research self-trust is made measurable and by applying the quantitative research method data are collected, anonymously among students based on a standardized questionnaire. People taking part in the survey are engineering students from various departments of BME Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences, who have enrolled for the optional subject of Learning and Lifelong Learning. The selection was aiming to include various engineering departments and it was assumed that the students who had enrolled for the subject were interested in the interaction between learning as an activity and the development of the career path.

The survey was conducted in two consecutive semesters.

In addition to questions relating to self-trust, students also answered questions about their needs for developing their competences and about their expectations with regard to the methodology of education. Alternative closed-ended questions on competency development were included in the online questionnaire, respondents were required to answer prioritizing multiple choice questions and open-ended questions.

On the one hand the survey results along with the comparative data from business were disclosed among the students concerned, and were evaluated with the tutor within the framework of the course. On the other hand, they are shared with business people, with the leaders of employers in the form of lectures and leadership training so that executives responsible for the integration of fresh graduates will see their own tasks and responsibility to develop the young workforce to meet their requirements. Last but not least the study intends to draw up key messages for higher education.

1. INNOVATION AND SELF-TRUST

A large-scale development of science and technology began in the twentieth century, which has further intensified in the 21st century, reinforcing the role of innovation and technological development both at the individual and organizational level.¹ The representatives of the engineering profession have a prominent role in this development, and higher education is facing a huge task in the education of engineers.

In the 21st century, not only the ability to develop is a requirement, technological advancement in different areas simultaneously creates competition and the need for co-operation between various actors. Creativity and innovation can result in novel methods, innovative or different ways of thinking, but at the same time, players in different industries are now forced to cooperate in certain areas of development, it is their well-understood interest to share the costs of development. The goal in every evolving industry is to find the state-of-the-art high-tech solution quickly and cost-effectively. In places where this works well - e.g. the Silicon Valley - a high degree of trust is a common characteristic both on the individual as on the organizational level.

Trust is a positive conviction that comes from the knowledge of the skills and values of another individual or organization. Trust can develop between two people when this conviction is reciprocal. Trust can accelerate processes; simplify collaboration thus resulting in lower costs. However, the ability to trust is based on self-trust. In order to be able to trust someone else, you have to be able to trust yourself first. The basis for our self-trust is to have a realistic self-image, based on which we can assess ourselves. To know our strengths and weaknesses, which ultimately result in our self-esteem that comes from our past experience and nourishes our self-trust with regard to challenges ahead in the present as well as in the future. This positive conviction nourishes our entrepreneurial spirit, our courage and our sense of responsibility.

2. TRUST AS A KEY COMPETENCE

Trust is a fundamental element of social capital – a key contributor to sustaining well-being outcomes, including economic development. (by Esteban Ortiz-Ospina and Max Roser) In a much cited article, Arrow (1972) says that "Virtually every commercial transaction has within itself an element of trust, certainly any transaction conducted over a period of time"².

Measures of trust from attitudinal survey questions remain the most common source of data on trust. Yet academic studies have shown that these measures of trust are generally weak predictors of actual trusting behaviour. Interestingly, however, questions about trusting attitudes do seem to predict

¹ Beszteri Béla: A 20. század mérlege és a 21. század esélyei

² Algan and Cahuc Trust, Institutions and Economic Development HANDBOOK OF ECONOMIC GROWTH 2013

trustworthiness. In other words, people who say they trust other people tend to be trustworthy themselves.³

OECD, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development started working out the project 'Defining and Selecting Key Competences: Theoretical and Conceptual Foundations with the participation of the Swiss Federal Bureau of Statistics and the United States Department of Education and the US Educational Statistics Center in 1997. International experts took part in the work, their analyses were arranged for publication⁴ by the organization and the compilation was simultaneously released in Canada, Germany, Switzerland and the United States.

The volume examines competences from a variety of perspectives and approaches. The theoretical approach of the concept of competence deals with general cognitive competences as intellectual abilities; special cognitive competencies, the existence of which offers the possibility to carry out an individual activity, such as driving a car. However, one of the various approaches and theories is the classification based on action competencies, which are at the same time the psychological conditions for a successful performance. The components of action competences are the general problem-solving ability, the ability to think critically, the possession of general and specific knowledge of a given situation, real and positive self-trust and social competences, which are often the outcome of school education. However their relevance exceeds formal education they are also important in everyday life. From the point of view of the subject of the study it is important to see that the theoretical approach classifies confidence as a constituent of action competences, which determine and influence our actions in different areas of work and private life. This theoretical approach also demonstrates that trust is not merely a feeling, but rather a measurable competence which can be established by behaviour frequency that basically affects efficiency in various fields of work and private life.

Education is at the heart of research at the Center of Educational Research and Innovation (CERI). They are seeking answers to indirect and direct questions related to future schools and universities in their comprehensive research which has been going on for many years.⁵

The aim of the project, which was developed in cooperation between OECD and CERI, "Learning Sciences and Brain Research", was to encourage cooperation between learning sciences and brain research, as well as between researchers and education policy.

Following the agreement with several research institutes, three conferences were held, focusing on "early learning", "young people's learning" and "adult learning". For the purposes of the present study it is worth highlighting and interpreting some statements included in the material of the three conferences.

The OECD study⁶ published in 2002 states that "successful learning is likely if a student has (a) high self-trust and self-esteem, (b) is strongly motivated for learning, and (c) his/her learning environment is characterized by "high challenge" and "low threat".

Learning fails when one (or more) of only four obstacles prevents success. The four learning obstacles are (i) lack of self-trust and self-esteem (the factor of well-being); (ii) poor motivation (does not "really want" to learn); (iii) real (or assumed) incomplete ability ("it is too difficult" or "I cannot do it"); (iv) lack of learning opportunities.

Referring to the opinions of a wide range of instructors, the publication states that the primary problem for students is self-trust and motivation. Self-trust and self-esteem are necessary but not sufficient conditions for motivation (the desire to really learn), the publication states.

3 Jones, E. (2013). Internationalization and employability: The role of intercultural experiences in the development of transferable skills. *Public Money & Management*, 33(2), 95-10

4 Defining and Selecting Key Competencies. Edited by Dominique Simone Rychen, Laura Hersch Salganik, 2001. Hogrefe and Huber Publishers (Seattle, Toronto, Bern, Göttingen).

5 <http://www.oecd.org/education/ceri/about/>

6 Understanding the Brain: Towards a New Learning Science OECD 2002

At the same time, in 2002, the OECD began examining good examples in eight countries (the UK, Australia, Denmark, Finland, Canada, Italy, Scotland and New Zealand) in terms of learning development methods which have proven successful in secondary education. The result of the inquiry in conjunction with the literature published in the various languages and the policy environment was published in several languages in 2005. In the chapter written by Janet Looney (Dylian Wiliam, King's College, London), the term "metacognition" is used to indicate that the learner is aware of how to think over and learn a subject. Learners having this ability can better target goals and develop their own learning strategy more consciously. This is supported by the results of the PISA Survey conducted in 2000, one of the most important conclusions of which was that in the absence of motivation and self-trust, students are unlikely to be able to develop such regulatory strategies.

In the 2005 study, several school teachers reported that cooperative learning, learning from each other in small groups, self-assessment, and feedback to each other not only increases learning efficiency but also promotes self-trust.

3. SELF-TRUST OF ENGINEERING STUDENTS

The survey related to the topic of the paper was conducted among engineering students at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME) Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences (GTK) in September 2017 and later in February 2018. The questions of the survey were the same as the online survey questions listed by the New York based global adult training company, FranklinCovey in order to allow for comparison between students' data and those of active players in the labour market.

As a pilot of an ongoing research, over the two consecutive semesters 20 and 14 students completed the questionnaires. When providing the average and variance values in the answers of the two groups we follow the chronological order, so the first number is always the result of the autumn group, and the second is of the spring group.

The online questionnaire, consisting of 12 questions, asks about key elements of **personal credibility** and **self-trust**, such as **integrity**, **intent**, **capabilities**, and **results**. The engineering students formed an opinion about themselves on the online site, anonymously. In relation to each key factor, they had to indicate by a value between 1 and 5 which of the two statements most expresses their own attitude and behaviour. Values 1 and 5 were expressed by 1 statement respectively. The results of the two groups were very similar with respect to each key factor.

With respect to *integrity* the questionnaire asked about trustworthy behaviour, respect for one's own and others' promises, behaviour according to their own values and principles. On a scale of five the average of the two groups is 3.48 and 3.62. For comparison, the average of the 150 respondents working in the competitive sector in Hungary is 4.41.

Students responded by giving a value from 1 to 5, where the highest average was given to the question where value (1) meant the statement, "*I often act differently from what I say*" while value (5) denoted the statement "*I act according to my values and my principles*". The average of the two groups was 4.00 and 3.92, with a coefficient of variation of 0.79 and 0.62 respectively. Response 1 was not marked by any respondent, while 25% and 14% of the respondents marked 5, acting according to his or her own values and principles.

Among the questions related to integrity, the students gave the lowest rate answers to the question where (1) meant that "*It is hard for me to admit that others might be right*", while the value (5) meant that "*I'm honestly open to consider new thoughts*". The average response rate for the two groups is 2.9 and 3.6, with a coefficient of variation of 1.16 and 1.09. Three of the larger group responded that they had difficulty in admitting that someone else might be right, which accounted for 15% of the respondents. There was no such student in the other group.

Undergraduate students are thus consistent in tracking their own values and principles, but it is difficult for them to admit that others may be right or have valuable new ideas. This phenomenon can be a barrier to collective creation. It is quite clear that responses of managers who are at the highest level in a hierarchy in a given organization represent a value higher by 0.86, averaging the value of the two groups, for integrity.

The questions asked about the second key factor of credibility, i.e. intent, investigated the students' attitudes in looking for balance between their individual goals and the consideration of the goals and interests of others. Here the average value of the two groups is 3.37 and 3.36, while the business leaders' average is 4.19.

Concerning questions relating to individual intent both groups are the strongest in their ability to care for others. With regard to the two statements, (1) "*I pretend to care about others*", (5) "*I sincerely care about others*" - the average of the two groups is 3.80 and 3.43. Generation researchers claim that the Y generation desire to belong to a team, are willing to become members of a team. This average result supports this claim and the coefficient of variation of 1.02 and 1.10 shows this generation's aspiration for independence and freedom. It is important to note that no respondent marked the value of 1, students do not pretend any other intentions than what they feel about others

The lowest average value among questions relating to the research of intentions, 3.1 was attributed to the statements on abundance at the autumn group, where statement (1) meant "*I behave as if there was not plenty of everything*" (money, opportunity, resource) , while (5) meant "*I behave as if there was plenty of everything*" (money, opportunity, resource). The abundance mentality is relevant in cooperation with others and entrepreneurial skills. If one can believe that there are enough resources and everyone can get enough, then he or she is able to enter a win-win cooperation. The lack of this attitude leads to a feeling of threat by scarcity, it undermines self-esteem and results in an urge to compete and defeat others.

The lowest average of the spring group, 3.29, relates to the two statements (1) "*I tend to consider only my own interests*", and (5) "*I take into account the interests of others*". This result is interesting because this group is also strong in the care of others concerning their response to questions of intent, but based on their responses taking into account the interests of others is not their strength.

As a result of responses to questions related to intent as a key element of personal credibility, it is apparent that, as with the survey results of research conducted on the behaviour of the millennials, the students participating in the survey have a strong intention to pursue their own goals and needs, and they turn to others in the intent of caring for them with the same attitude.

In our interactions with others, we judge others based on their behaviour, while we judge ourselves based on our intentions. Intention is not loud in itself if we do not communicate it, or if we do not express it correctly and consciously, others will only judge us based on our behaviour. For this reason, students participating in engineering education can benefit from work in small groups, from project tasks requiring co-operation, where they have to match their own goals to others' goals. The knowledge gained in these tasks gives them an opportunity to acquire useful self-knowledge and self-assessment experiences.

The first two key factors of self-trust, *integrity* and *intent* derive from the character, while the next two key factors, *abilities* and *results* are related to competence. In assessing a person's trustworthiness, the higher level of self-knowledge the students are at for the first two factors, the more they can realistically judge themselves. Self-knowledge can be most efficiently developed by experience. Students receive less feedback from higher education in this field, as opposed to the other two key factors, in particular the results. This is also supported by research findings.

Within the field of responses to competency questions, obtained results reflect on the attitudes required to achieve results as a measure of one of the key factors of self-trust, and these are the best average results obtained in the survey. The average result of the two consecutive groups is 3.75 and 3.57 on a scale of 1-5, while that of business leaders is 4.61. This tendency can also be observed among the participants working in high ranking leading positions in businesses. responses around the topic of results show the highest scores comparing responses related to the four key factors.

The autumn group response to two statements provided the same average score of 3.85 as the highest value; the spring group also estimated themselves with the highest average of 3.93 with their answers to the same statements. One of these statement pairs is (1) *"I cannot always be counted on"* and (5) *"I'm totally trustworthy"* with the coefficient of variation of 1.09 in the autumn group and 0.997 in the spring group. The other set of high average values for the spring group is (1) *"I set the benchmark at a low level"* and (5) *"I aim at success"* with an average of 3.71.

In the light of the a.m. data, it can be concluded that according to their own assessment the students' self-trust is based on their reliability and result orientation. In higher education, it is worth paying attention to and giving feedback on this positive conviction and the manifestations of these two skills so that the students are aware of their strengths. If students receive more positive feedback, it increases not just their self-trust, but also their trust in their teachers and higher education.

As a last factor, students are required to interpret their own answers related to their own skills. Both groups evaluated themselves lower in relation to the statement pairs related to their skills than in the case of statements about result orientation and the same trend can be observed in the responses of business leaders as well. The average of the responses of the two groups is 3.13 and 3.12 respectively compared to the average of 4.42 for business executives.

In this group of questions, the lowest value (2.55 and 2.93) with the highest coefficient of variation (1.317 and 1.328) is achieved by the responses to the statements (1) *"I do not know where I'm heading in life"* (5) *"I know exactly where I want to get"*. Within this group of questions the highest scores (3.55 and 3.21) are reached by the responses to the statements (1) *"I lack the abilities necessary to perform my duties."* (5) *"I have all the necessary abilities to accomplish my tasks"* with a coefficient of variation of 1.19 and 1.12 respectively.

In the 21st century scopes of activities, jobs disappear and are restructured, digitalisation is expected to further shape the labour market. Students' parents who are employees do not work in the same workplace or job during a lifetime. Students have very few examples around themselves, in virtual or real life, which are helpful in planning their life career. During classroom discussions with the students, it turned out that their acquaintances who graduated as engineers have an unimaginable variety of jobs: they are executives in their own ventures working in various fields, or make a living as actors and other occupations not requiring engineering competencies. This variety of patterns is more alarming for students than inspirational.

One must not ignore the fact that in comparing the attitudes needed to achieve the results - *"I believe in myself, I am trustworthy"* - and the assessment of ability - *"I have all the necessary abilities to accomplish my tasks"* - the answers of the people at the top of the hierarchy showed similar tendencies.

In examining our competencies, we are most subjective when we assess our own abilities; it is most difficult to assess our own capabilities realistically.

Finally, when examining the self-trust values calculated as the aggregate result of the four key factors, it is apparent that for the 11 executives at the top of their career participating in the survey, their positive convictions about their own selves were the strongest. The value of their responses converted gives a result of 91.34%. Their direct reports, the 139 top-ranking leaders' self-trust index is 85.18%, whereas those of the two groups of engineering students participating in the survey are almost the same, 68.67% and 68.33% respectively.

All in all, we can say that our achievements and our success at work strengthen our self-trust. If the labour market confirms our knowledge and abilities by offering the potential to be promoted to a high ranking position, it strengthens our self-esteem. However, not every fresh graduate can expect to have a leadership position, so it is very important that the self-image and self-assessment of newly graduated students just entering the labour market does not depend on the feedback of the outside world, they should rather be aware of their abilities, strengths and weaknesses.

4. CONCLUSION

OECD studies and the various studies carried out by the pedagogical profession emphasize the importance of self-trust in the efficiency of learning. Higher education can start educating students who have been studying for 12 years, who already have a learning experience, more or less good self-image and self-esteem, and have a vision of their own future, or are expecting it from university years.

Engineering education faces these challenges and tries to meet the expectations of the labour market as best as they can by designing the best training content and methodology. The present study aims to contribute to this by providing a non-exhaustive summary of the research related to the subject and by presenting specific research results.

It can be established that, in academic education, in addition to theoretical education, work in small groups, project tasks and cooperative research work have to play an increasingly important role. As part of this cooperative work, students need to get the most feedback possible from their instructors and from each other. This not only improves their self-assessment, it not only helps to raise awareness of their strengths and competencies to be developed, but also enhances the ability to give and receive feedback, which will become one of their most valuable assets in the world of work.

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